

COMPLICATIONS AFTER LIVER RESECTIONS-BILIRAGHIA

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Abstract

Liver surgery is historically one of the "youngest" areas in abdominal surgery, but at the same time it marks very rapid progress and continuous development, which continues even today.

The International Study Group of Liver Surgery (ISGLS) provides definitions and criteria for

The assessment of Specific postresection complications. Any condition in which the drainage secretion contains bilirubin > 3 mg / dl (51.5 μ mol / l) and a ratio of drainage bilirubin / serum bilirubin > 3 on the 3rd postoperative day - the so-called 3 $\times$ 3 rule. This is the most common SPRU, which can be effectively drained (biliary fistula formation), but can be extremely dangerous due to retention in the peritoneal cavity - bilioma, abscess, biliary peritonitis, sepsis. There are three degrees of biliragy depending on the severity of the condition: Grade A - does not require or requires minimal change in the treatment strategy of the patient; Grade B - requires a change in the patient's treatment strategy (diagnostic and / or interventional procedures), but does not require re-laparotomy or biliarygia grade "A", with a statute of limitations > 7 days; Grade C - requires re-laparotomy.

Keywords: liver resections, complications after liver resections, biliary

Introduction

Prerequisites for the rapid development of liver resection surgery are the established anatomical knowledge of segmental hepatic anatomy, the improvement of techniques for parenchymal dissection and definitive hemo- and biliostasis, the improvement of hepatoprotection methods and means, the development of anesthesia and resuscitation care for operated patients.

Objective

Determination of a possible prognostic role of the type of liver resection (anatomic or atypical) for the risk of occurrence, frequency and severity of postoperative specific complications-biliraghia.

Materials and methods

For the period from January, 2007 - March, 2018 in Clinic of liver, biliary pancreatic and general surgery, Acibadem City Clinic Tokuda Hospital ,1021 interventions were performed on the liver:

Cases of intervention other than liver resection by definition were excluded ISGLS, "removal of part of the liver parenchyma due to involvement by a disease process or traumatic injury resulting in devitalization of the parenchyma".

Thus, the study did not find the cases of:

- hepatotomy;
- cystotomies and cyst resections, practically without removal of functioning or pathologically

altered liver parenchyma;

- liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors. liver biopsies, alcoholization of tumors;

- interruption of trunk branches of the hepatic artery and/or portal vein with the aim of hypoperfusion of a given area (segments, lobe);

- suture of the liver in trauma;

Thus, a total of 852 cases of liver resections were included in the series

Bilirrhagia is the most common complication, varying in a very wide range – from 3.6 to 33%. [1,2,3,4,5,6,10,] In addition to the high frequency and secondary complications that bilirubin can lead to, the other factor that determines its importance is intraperitoneal septic complications, liver failure and not in the last place and a fatal outcome.

Results

Bilirrhagia, both in our study and according to literature data, is a more frequently observed complication than bleeding, but on the other hand, it is not as dangerous as bleeding. In our series, we reported postresection bilirubin in a total of 17 patients, and it was most common after anatomic liver resection as a stand-alone procedure (5.2%) compared with atypical resection (0.9%). In multivisceral resections, post-resection bilirubin was reported with approximately the same frequency – 1.8% after Anat. resection and 1.7% after Atypical. / Table 1 /

Table 1.

Frequency of postoperative bilirubin after liver resection

Друга операция	Билирагия	Статистика	АнатЧР	АтипЧР	Общо	P
Не	Не	N	110	217	327	0,023
		%	94,8%	99,1%	97,6%	
	Да	N	6	2	8	
		%	5,2%	,9%	2,4%	
Да	Не	N	112	397	509	1,000
		%	98,2%	98,3%	98,3%	
	Да	N	2	7	9	
		%	1,8%	1,7%	1,7%	

The severity of post-operative bilirubin is as follows:

Grade A – 8 patients in whom the flow rate of the drained bile was on average between 50-350 ml/24h. Leaving contact drains to the resection surface of the liver in these cases lasted an average of 15.2 days (12-36 days). This "waiting" (up to 36 days) was used when there was a tendency to decrease the amount of secretion, as well as in the absence of evidence of an acute surgical abdomen, a stable general condition and the absence of intra-abdominal collections established by ultrasound.

Grade B – 7 patients in whom an interventional procedure was performed to control the complication. In three of them, a puncture was performed under ultrasound control and evacuation of a formed perihepatic collection. In the remaining four patients, it was necessary to perform ERCP with papillosphincterotomy and stenting of the extrahepatic bile ducts.

Grade C – 2 patients were reoperated. One developed diffuse biliary peritonitis after right hemihepatectomy. The patient made a full recovery and was discharged on the 9th day after reoperation. The second relaparotomy was due to high-flow bilirubin.

When examining the data on post-resection bilirubin, we found the following patterns.

- reduction of its frequency - below 10%;
- resolution of complications with conservative methods or with an interventional procedure - puncture under ultrasound control; ERCP, papillotomy and

stenting of the bile ducts; percutaneous transhepatic cholangiography and placement of an external biliary drain.

Most studies show the statistical significance of more than 10 risk factors for the occurrence of post-resection bilirubin. [7,9,11,12,13,15-20]

- traumatization of Glisson's capsule
- resection surface area ≥ 57.5 cm²;
- re-hepatectomy;
- intraoperative blood loss ≥ 775 ml;
- intraoperative bilirubin;
- operative time ≥ 300 min;
- peripheral cholangiocarcinoma;
- preoperative chemoembolization;
- others

Discussion

Of the patients operated on, we found bilirubin in 17 of them. Anatomical liver resection as a stand-alone procedure has a higher risk of bilirubin (5.2%) compared to atypical resection (0.9%). The low incidence of bilirubin is due to the use of external biliary drainage to prevent postoperative biliary hypertension.

The more frequent resolution of postoperative Grade B bilirubin (n=7/17) with an interventional procedure: punctures under ultrasound control of a formed collection /Fig 1./ and Endoscope Retrograde Cholangiopancreatography /ERCP/ with papillosphincterotomy and stenting of the bile ducts.

КТОМИЯ

Fig.1. Puncturing and drainage of bilioma under ultrasound control

Conclusion

Liver resection surgery should be performed in centers with sufficient experience in this field, working according to established standards and algorithms, and also with well-developed interventional gastroenterology.

Post-resection bilirubin develops more often after Anat. liver resections compared to Atypical as independent procedures (5.2% vs. 0.9%, respectively), while after multivisceral resections this complication has the same frequency – 1.8% after Anat. and 1.7% after Atypical resections.

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